

Spectral Intensities and Bonding Parameters for some Praseodymium(III) and Neodymium(III) Complexes with Benzimidazoles

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The electronic spectral intensity parameters (Judd-Ofelt; T_{λ}) calculated from absorption spectral data for the complexes of praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) nitrates with benzimidazole and 2-methyl-, 2-ethyl- and 2-n-propyl-benzimidazoles are reported. The conductance of these derivatives in dimethylformamide suggests 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The infrared spectral data indicate the presence of C_{av} as well as D_{sh} -nitrate ions in the complexes. The correlation of the intensity of hypersensitive transitions with bonding (nephelauxetic ratio and degree of covalency) parameters are also reported.

ELECTRONIC spectral intensity parameters¹ (Judd-Ofelt; T_{λ}) are characteristic of $f \leftrightarrow f$ transitions in lanthanide ions. The behaviour of these parameters under the influence of different ligand fields have been investigated by several workers²⁻⁷. However, very few studies have been reported pertaining to the coordination of *N*-heterocyclic ligands in this respect.

In this communication, preparation of the complexes of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} with benzimidazole and its 2-alkyl derivatives and their characterisation data (electrolytic conductance and infrared spectra) and intensity parameters calculated from oscillator strength (P) of intra- f^n -transitions by using partial multiple regression method⁸ are reported. The effect of alkyl chain length on covalent bonding of the ligands with metal ions has been studied on the basis of correlation between hypersensitivity of $f \leftrightarrow f$ transition with nephelauxetic ratio (β) as well as covalency parameter ($b^{1/2}$).

Experimental

Preparation of ligands: Benzimidazole, 2-methyl-, 2-ethyl- and 2-propyl-benzimidazoles were prepared according to the reported procedure⁹.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes were prepared by mixing the ethyl acetate solutions of metal nitrate (praseodymium or neodymium nitrate hexahydrate, 0.8702 and 0.8766 g) and ligands (benzimidazole, 2-methyl-, 2-ethyl- and 2-propyl-benzimidazole, 1.0622, 1.1881, 1.3143, 1.4398 g) respectively in 1 : 4.5 molar ratio and refluxing the solution for 5-6 h. The separated sticky solids were washed several times with ethyl acetate. Crystalline derivatives were finally obtained by treating with ether and scratching with glass rod.

The products were collected by filtration and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Conductivities in dimethyl formamide were measured on a Systronic conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded in the range 4 000-200 cm^{-1} on a Perkin-Elmer 599 spectrophotometer. Electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in ethanol were measured in the range of 300-900 nm on a Pye-Unicam SP8-100 spectrophotometer. An Apple I computer was used for computation of the intensity parameters from electronic absorption spectral data.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) of the complexes indicated $ML_x(NO_3)_3 \cdot nH_2O$ formulation. Where $M = Pr^{III}$, and Nd^{III} ; $L =$ benzimidazole (BzImH), 2-methylbenzimidazole (MeBzIm); $X = 3$ and $n = 3, 4$ or 5 ; for $L = 2$ -ethylbenzimidazole (EtBzIm) and 2-propylbenzimidazole (PrBzIm), $X = 2$ and $n = 4$ or 5 , the molar conductance data in dimethyl formamide fall in the range 110-121 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ expected for uni-univalent electrolytes¹⁰. The stoichiometry of the complexes seems to be affected by chain length of 2-alkyl group of the benzimidazoles. The long alkyl chains such as 2-ethyl and 2-propyl cause steric hinderance in crystal packing for which 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry is preferred in their complexes as compared to the 1 : 3 stoichiometry for the complexes with BzImH and MeBzIm.

Infrared spectra: The ir bands in the region 3 500-3 200 cm^{-1} are ascribed to $\nu_{as}(OH)$ of water molecules in the complexes. The positions of $\nu_{as} N-H$ (3 150-3 000), δ_{NH} (1 420-1 400) and $\nu_{as} C-N$ (1 620-1 600 cm^{-1}) vibrational modes of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA FOR Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} COMPLEXES WITH BENZIMIDAZOLES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
	Metal	N
Pr(BzImH) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	19.20 (19.16)	17.10 (17.14)
Pr(MeBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	17.75 (17.71)	15.90 (15.84)
Pr(EtBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	20.35 (20.35)	14.25 (14.18)
Pr(PrBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	19.00 (19.10)	13.29 (13.29)
Nd(BzImH) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	19.98 (19.96)	16.66 (16.66)
Nd(MeBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	18.47 (18.47)	16.13 (16.20)
Nd(EtBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	20.72 (20.76)	14.21 (14.11)
Nd(PrBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	19.90 (19.95)	13.60 (13.56)

the ligands and complexes are very much similar. The presence of ν_{as} NH modes for the complexes supports the presence of imino (N₂H) proton. Hence the metal ions are coordinated through tertiary (N₃) nitrogen atom of benzimidazole nucleus. The 420–412 cm⁻¹ band is assigned to M–N stretching¹¹.

The presence of absorption bands in the region 1 390–1 370 and 840–815 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_3(E')$ and $\nu_2(A''_2)$ vibrational modes of D_{3h}-nitrate. A strong multiplet around 1 530–1 450 cm⁻¹ and a medium intensity band at 1 328–1 270 cm⁻¹ are clearly distinguishable from the ligand bands and are attributed to $\nu_4(B_1)$ and $\nu_1(A_1)$, respectively, for C_{2v}-nitrate. The difference between these absorption frequencies ($\nu_4 - \nu_1$) is 180–210 cm⁻¹ which is the range reported for bidentate coordinated nitrate group. The weak absorption bands at 1 030–1 000 and 815–780 cm⁻¹ are attributed to $\nu_3(A_1)$ and $\nu_6(B_2)$ vibrational modes, respectively. The medium intensity band at 720–700 cm⁻¹ is identified as a $\nu_6(B_1)$ vibrational mode of the nitrate group. Thus the infrared spectral data support the presence of both ionic as well as bidentately coordinated nitrate groups in these complexes.

Electronic spectra: Absorption maxima of all the complexes show a red-shift indicating the co-

ordination of ligands with metal ions. The electronic spectral data for the Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} complexes were analysed to calculate the Judd–Ofelt or intensity parameters² (T_λ).

The values of T_λ parameters have been computed from Judd–Ofelt expression by using partial multiple regression method⁹ where the values of reduced matrix elements [$U^{(\lambda)}$]² have been taken from literature¹. The T_λ parameters are considered to be characteristic of a particular lanthanide complex. The r.m.s. deviations between the observed and calculated values of P (oscillator strength)¹² for Pr^{III} $\pm 0.10 \times 10^{-6}$ to $\pm 0.31 \times 10^{-6}$ and for Nd^{III} $\pm 0.22 \times 10^{-6}$ to $\pm 0.61 \times 10^{-6}$ proves that Judd–Ofelt relation is applicable in the form of equation (1),

$$P = \sum T_\lambda \nu (f^n \psi_i \| U^{(\lambda)} \| f^n \psi_j)^2 \quad (1)$$

($\lambda = 2, 4, 6$) for the complex derivatives reported. There is a little variation in the values of T_2 for these complexes and the ratio of T_4/T_6 for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} derivatives are fairly constant, i.e. 0.201 and 0.473, respectively. On the basis of these observations it can be concluded that both Pr and Nd ions possess the same coordination number in the complexes formed by benzimidazole and its alkyl derivatives, despite the difference in the metal–ligand stoichiometry.

The hypersensitive transitions (which are sensitive to environmental changes) $^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_2$ of Pr^{III} and $^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}$ of Nd^{III} have been found to be proportional to nephelauxetic ratio β ; it is calculated according to relation $\bar{\nu}_c/\bar{\nu}_f$, where $\bar{\nu}_c$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ are energies in cm⁻¹ of the electronic transition in complex and free ion, respectively. From the perusal of Table 2 it is evident that the value of β decreases with decreasing frequency of the transition as reported for rare earth ions¹³.

The degree of covalency ($b^{1/2}$) which is a measure of the degree of mixing of the metal ($4f$) with ligand wave functions is related to β according to: $b^{1/2} = [1/2(1-\beta)]^{1/2}$. Positive and negative values of $b^{1/2}$ for a complex corresponds to its covalent and ionic character, respectively. The positive values of $b^{1/2}$ for the present complexes (Table 2) show covalent nature of metal–ligand bond. The value of $b^{1/2}$ increases in the following

TABLE 2—COMPUTED VALUES OF T_λ , P_{expt} , β AND $b^{1/2}$ PARAMETERS OF Pr^{III} AND Nd^{III} COMPLEXES WITH BENZIMIDAZOLES

Compd.	T_2 $\times 10^{10}$	T_4 $\times 10^{10}$	T_6 $\times 10^{10}$	T_4/T_6	Energy cm ⁻¹	P_{expt} $\times 10^6$	β	$b^{1/2}$
Pr(BzImH) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	-37.62	8.30	39.64	0.209	22 497	11.76	0.971 3	0.119 7
Pr(MeBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	-81.68	7.74	39.95	0.193	22 485	11.79	0.970 8	0.120 8
Pr(EtBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	-46.17	8.02	40.30	0.199	22 472	11.89	0.970 2	0.121 8
Pr(PrBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·5H ₂ O	-57.01	8.01	40.15	0.199	22 446	11.94	0.969 1	0.124 2
Nd(BzImH) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	8.21	4.88	9.85	0.495	17 218	15.75	0.995 3	0.048 4
Nd(MeBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	7.76	5.07	9.92	0.511	17 182	16.61	0.993 1	0.058 7
Nd(EtBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	8.00	5.32	11.70	0.454	17 179	16.90	0.993 0	0.059 1
Nd(PrBzIm) ₃ (NO ₃) ₃ ·4H ₂ O	6.72	5.87	11.25	0.521	17 177	17.10	0.992 9	0.059 5

order of ligands, $M - BzImH < M - MeBzIm < M - EtBzIm < M - PrBzIm$, indicating that coordinating ability of ligand increases with the increase in alkyl chain length of benzimidazoles.

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References

1. W. T. CARNALL, P. R. FIELDS and B. G. WYBOURNE, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 3797.
2. C. K. JORGENSEN, "Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes", Pergamon, Oxford, 1962.
3. B. G. WYBOURNE, "Spectroscopic Properties of Rare Earths", Wiley, New York, 1965.
4. G. H. DICKE, "Spectra and Energy Levels of Rare Earth Ions in Crystals", Wiley, New York, 1968.
5. W. T. CARNALL, P. R. FIELDS and K. RAJNAK, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 4413, 4424, 4443.
6. S. P. TONDON, P. P. VAISHNAVA and R. C. MATHUR, *Sol. State Comm.*, 1974, **15**, 787.
7. S. P. TONDON and P. P. VAISHNAVA, *Can. J. Spectrosc.*, 1977, **22**, 17.
8. C. H. GAULDEN, "Methods of Statistical Analysis", Asia Publishing House, Bombay, 1964, Chap. 8, p. 134.
9. M. A. PHILLIPS, MAY and BAKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2393.
10. W. J. GRARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
11. J. H. FORSBERG and T. MOELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 883.
12. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1968, Chap. 6, p. 147.
13. R. D. PRACOCK, *Struct. Bonding*, 197b, **22**, 88.